

LABORATORY INCUBATION EXPERIMENT TO ASSESS THE SUITABILITY OF CEMENT KILN DUST FOR CROP PRODUCTION

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Abstract

In order to develop an integrated solid waste management strategy for cement factory waste (cement kiln dust, or CKD), a lab experiment was conducted to study the influence of CKD and amendments on soil properties for a duration of 60 days in red (Irugur soil series) and black soils (Periyanaickenpalayam soil series). The results revealed that the application of CKD alone at a rate of 10 metric tonnes (MT) ha⁻¹ negatively impacted soil bulk density, soil salinity, available N, organic C, and soil microbial properties (total bacteria, fungi, and actinomycetes population) while it narrowed down the pH of soils. Increased content of NH₄OAc-K from 224 to 426 in the Irugur soil series and from 352 to 560 kg ha⁻¹ in the Periyanaickenpalayam soil series were recorded due to the application of CKD at the rate of 10 MT ha⁻¹ with press-mud (5 MT ha⁻¹). Application of CKD at the rate of 5 MT ha⁻¹ with coir-pith improved soil bulk density; farmyard manure (FYM) increased the soil organic C; green leaf manure increased soil microbial properties (total bacteria, fungi, and actinomycetes population) in both soils. The discovery demonstrated that CKD can be used as a potential source for recycling in agriculture at a rate of 5 MT ha⁻¹ with organic amendments while not affecting soil properties.

Keywords: lab study, CKD, amendments, bulk density, soil reaction, available N, organic C, microbial count

Introduction

Indiscriminate disposal of industrial waste affected the air, plant, soil, and groundwater ecosystems. CKD is one such industrial waste (fine powdery material appearing similar to Portland cement) formed during the manufacture of cement. CKD contains high amounts of Cl and K, rendering it unsuitable for recycling as raw material for Portland cement production (Seo *et al.*, 2019). The presence of elements other than Ca/Mg may reduce purity and make CKD unsuitable for use as a raw material (Albahari *et al.*, 2022). Part of CKD is reused in cement plants, and the rest is landfilled (Kunal *et al.*, 2012). Due to increased pressure on land and ever-increasing disposal costs, the utilization of CKD in highway uses, soil stabilization, waste treatment, controlled low-strength material (CLSM), cement mortar/concrete, *etc.*, has become an attractive alternative to its disposal. Rodd *et al.* (2009) reported that CKD may be used as an amendment in agriculture.

To produce one MT of cement, around 0.06 – 0.07 MT of CKD is generated. Global cement production is expected to increase from 3.27 billion MT in 2010 to 4.83 billion metric t in 2030; with approximately 220 million MT of CKD discarded annually from cement manufacturing facilities (Elbaz *et al.*, 2019).

Cement kiln dust (CKD) is rich in essential plant nutrients such as P, K, Ca, Mg, Cu, Zn, Fe, Mn, *etc.*, (Prabakaran, 2019) The use of CKD for crop production is a method of waste recycling for a circular economy where valuable nutrients are recycled back into the ecosystem (Prabakaran, 2019). Recycling is one of the efficient methods of waste management that can be included in an integrated waste management strategy. (Prabakaran, 2006; Prabakaran, 2007). Agriculture is also faced with constraints like fertilizer problems and a lack of knowledge about CKD limits its use in agriculture (Sett, 2017). Sugar industrial waste (press mud) (Sunilkumar *et al.*, 2017), and paper factory sludge (Udayasoorian *et al.*, 2007) have been used in agriculture (Prabakaran, 2021). The information regarding the influence of CKD on soil properties was necessary to develop, an integrated solid waste management strategy for CKD. Hence, a lab study was initiated to study the influence of CKD on physical properties (bulk density), physicochemical properties (pH, EC), chemical properties (organic C, available NPK), and, biological properties (total bacteria, fungal, and actinomycetes populations).

Table 1. Characteristics of CKD

	Properties	Range value	Average
1	State	Pellets–Powder	Powder
2	Colour	White–light gray	Light gray

Materials and method

Samples were collected from a leading cement factory in Dalmiapuram of Ariyalur district of Tamil Nadu at fixed intervals to study the properties of CKD; analyzed for their physical, chemical, and biological properties by following standard procedures in the Soil Science and Agricultural Chemistry Lab, Agricultural Engineering and Research Institute, Kumulur, Ariyalur District.

For conducting the lab study, two types of soil were used: red sandy soil (Irugur soil series) and black cotton soil (Periyanaickenpalayam series). The initial pH, EC, CEC, available N, Olson P, NH₄OAc K, organic C, and bulk density of red sandy soil (Irugur soil series) and black cotton soil (Periyanaickenpalayam series) were 7.5 and 9.5; 0.19 and 0.35 dS m⁻¹, 8.5 and 35 c mol. (p⁺) kg⁻¹; 163 and 176 kg ha⁻¹; 9.0 and 18.5 kg ha⁻¹; 224 and 332 kg ha⁻¹; 0.25 and 0.32 percent; 1.37 and 1.33 MT m⁻³, respectively.

The following treatments were imposed: T₁-Control; T₂-CKD@5 MT ha⁻¹; T₃-CKD@10 MT ha⁻¹ T₄-T₂+FYM @12.5 MT ha⁻¹; T₅-T₂+Green manure@6.25 MT ha⁻¹; T₆-T₂+ composted coir-pith@5 MT ha⁻¹; T₇-T₂+composted press-mud@5 MT ha⁻¹; T₈-T₃+FYM @12.5 MT ha⁻¹; T₉-T₃+green manure@6.25 MT ha⁻¹. T₁₀-T₃+composed coir-pith@5 MT ha⁻¹; T₁₁-T₃+composted press-mud@5 MT ha⁻¹. The experiment was replicated thrice. The required quantity of CKD was obtained from Dalmia Cement, Dalmia Puram, Ariyalur district. Composted coir-pith was obtained for Pollachi, and composted press-mud was obtained from EID Parry and used for the lab experiment. About 500 g of soil was filled in plastic cups (one-liter capacity), and the required quantity of amendments was added according to the treatments. Soil moisture was maintained below field capacity. These plastic cups are placed inside the lab under room conditions. Observations were recorded for 60 days after incubation. The laboratory experiment was carried out in a completely randomized design (CRD) with three replications. All of the experiments were statistically evaluated using an ANOVA table. The critical difference was worked out at a 5 percent (0.05) probability, or corrections among parameters were at a 95% significant level.

Results and discussions

From the table, it was found that the CKD was alkaline in nature (pH = 9.9); devoid of N but rich in Ca, Mg, K, Cl, and SO₃ (Table 1).

3	Bulk density (MT m ⁻³)	1.14–1.16	1.15
4	Specific gravity (MT m ⁻³)	2.6–2.9	2.81
5	EC (dS m ⁻¹)	1.25–3.50	2.50
6	pH	7.90–11.90	9.90
7	N (%)	0.00	0.00
8	P (%)	0.02–0.80	0.05
9	K (%)	3.0–6.0	4.00
10	Ca (%)	12–18	15.0
11	Mg (%)	2.00–8.0	6.00
12	Na (%)	0.02–0.07	0.05
13	Cl ⁻ (%)	7.6–16.2	11.6
14	SO ₃ (%)	4–11	5.2
15	SiO ₂ (%)	8–13	9.5

The bulk density of the soil was negatively influenced by the application of CKD at an increased level (10 MT ha⁻¹) (Table 2), while the application of CKD with coir-pith (10 MT ha⁻¹) improved the bulk density in both soils (decreased from 1.45 to 1.36 and from 1.40 to 1.36 MTm⁻³ in Irugur soil series and Periyanaickenpalayam series, respectively). The increase in bulk density due to the application of CKD may be due to the presence of calcium.

Soil infiltration, available water capacity, soil porosity, rooting depth or rooting restrictions, soil microorganism activity, root proliferation,

and nutrient availability are determined by soil bulk density. An increasing bulk density implies a decrease in macropores and an increase in meso- and micropores. A strong and negative relationship between soil organic matter and bulk density was reported. In this study, it was found that with the decrease in organic C, there was an increase in the soil bulk density.

Table 2. Effect of CKD and amendments on soil bulk density under lab study (at 60 DAI)

Treatments	Bulk density (MT m ⁻³)	
	Irugur soil series	Periyanaickenpalayam series
Control (absolute)	1.45	1.40
CKD@5 MT ha ⁻¹	1.46	1.45
CKD @10 MT ha ⁻¹	1.48	1.47
CKD@5 MT ha ⁻¹ +FYM@ 12.5 MT ha ⁻¹	1.41	1.37
CKD@5 MT ha ⁻¹ +Green manure@6.25 MT ha ⁻¹	1.42	1.39
CKD@5 MT ha ⁻¹ + Composted coir-pith @ 10 MT ha ⁻¹	1.36	1.36
CKD@5 MT ha ⁻¹ +Press mud @ 5 MT ha ⁻¹	1.42	1.37
CKD@10 MT ha ⁻¹ +FYM @12.5 MT ha ⁻¹	1.38	1.40
CKD@10 MT ha ⁻¹ + Green manure@6.25 MT ha ⁻¹	1.42	1.40
CKD@10 MT ha ⁻¹ + Composted coir-pith @ 10 MT ha ⁻¹	1.38	1.40
CKD@10 MT ha ⁻¹ +Press- mud @ 5 MT ha ⁻¹	1.42	1.41
SEd	0.02	0.02
CD	0.04	0.04

Soil pH was found to increase in Irugur soil series (from 7.18 to 8.72), while it decreased in Periyanaickenpalayam series (from 9.51 to 8.63) due to the application of CKD. An increase in pH due to the deposition of CKD in acid soil was reported (Lamare and Singh, 2020). Higher EC values were recorded due to the application of

composted press-mud with 10 MT of CKD in both soils. Increased EC content in this present study might be due to increased salinity of the CKD and press-mud. An increase in EC due to the application of press-mud was recorded (Gulam *et al.*, 2010).

Table 3. Effect of CKD on soil pH and EC (at 60 DAI) under lab study

Treatments	pH	EC dSm ⁻¹
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	Irugur soil series	Periyanaickenpalayam series	Irugur soil series	Periyanaickenpalayam series
Control (absolute)	7.18	9.51	0.19	0.35
CKD@5 MT ha ⁻¹	8.31	8.94	0.58	0.71
CKD @10 MT ha ⁻¹	8.72	8.52	0.79	0.82
CKD@5 MT ha ⁻¹ +FYM@ 12.5 MT ha ⁻¹	8.00	8.76	0.59	0.91
CKD@5 MT ha ⁻¹ +Green manure@6.25 MT ha ⁻¹	7.90	8.75	0.44	0.83
CKD@5 MT ha ⁻¹ + Composted coir-pith @10 MT ha ⁻¹	8.42	9.38	0.82	1.02
CKD@5MTha+Press mud @ 5 MT ha ⁻¹	8.52	8.94	0.94	0.90
CKD@10 MT ha ⁻¹ +FYM @12.5 MT ha ⁻¹	8.33	8.74	0.75	1.01
CKD@10 MT ha ⁻¹ + Green manure@6.25 MT ha ⁻¹	8.22	8.63	0.52	0.94
CKD@10 MT ha + Composted coir-pith @10 MT ha ⁻¹	8.51	8.64	0.95	1.05
CKD@10 MT ha ⁻¹ +Press- mud @ 5 MT ha ⁻¹	8.66	8.67	0.99	1.15
SEd	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.02
CD	0.24	0.04	0.04	0.04

It was observed that organic C and available N decreased in both soils due to the application of CKD at 10 MT ha⁻¹. A decrease in available N and organic C might be due to the loss of N (through ammonia volatilization) at an increased pH (Mandal *et al.* 2016). The soil P was found to be non-significantly different due to the application of CKD

in both soils (Table 4). The addition of 10 MT ha⁻¹ CKD and 5 MT ha⁻¹ press-mud increased the NH₄OAc-K. The increase in NH₄OAc-K in the present study is due to the high content of K in the CKD and press-mud. Negim *et al.* (2016) reported increased K content due to the application of press-mud.

Table 4. Effect of CKD and amendments on soil properties under lab study (at 60 DAI)

Treatments	Organic C %		Avail. N kg/ha		Olson P kg/ha		NH ₄ OAc-K kg/ha	
	Irugur soil series	Periyanaickenpalayam series	Irugur soil series	Periyanaickenpalayam series	Irugur soil series	Periyanaickenpalayam series	Irugur soil series	Periyanaickenpalayam series
Control (absolute)	0.25	0.31	157	176	5.0	16.0	224	352
CKD@5 MT ha ⁻¹	0.24	0.28	163	163	6.0	19.2	350	450
CKD @10 MT ha ⁻¹	0.21	0.23	151	176	6.7	21.4	398	510
CKD@5 MT ha ⁻¹ +FYM@ 12.5 MT ha ⁻¹	0.31	0.31	176	188	11.0	26.6	345	492
CKD@5 MT ha ⁻¹ +Green manure@6.25 MT ha ⁻¹	0.27	0.29	188	188	9.5	25.2	386	488
CKD@5 MT ha ⁻¹ + Composted coir-pith @10 MT ha ⁻¹	0.29	0.29	176	188	7.5	24.4	382	480
CKD@5 MT ha+Press mud @ 5 MT ha ⁻¹	0.26	0.29	176	188	14.0	28.8	414	528
CKD@10 MT ha ⁻¹ +FYM @12.5 MT ha ⁻¹	0.30	0.29	176	188	11.0	22.2	388	490
CKD@10 MT ha ⁻¹ + Green manure@6.25 MT ha ⁻¹	0.27	0.25	176	188	11.0	22.4	396	502
CKD@10 MT ha + Composted coir-pith @10 MT ha ⁻¹	0.23	0.25	163	200	9.5	25.2	396	502
CKD@10 MT ha ⁻¹ +Press- mud @ 5 MT ha ⁻¹	0.29	0.25	176	188	19.0	28.8	426	560
SEd	0.01	0.01	1.92	5.66	0.50	0.40	4.5	4.5
CD	0.02	0.02	4.0	NS	NS	NS	9.63	9.6

In general, more bacteria and actinomycetes populations were noticed in the Periyanaickenpalayam series than in the Irugur soil series during the lab study. A higher fungal population was observed in the Irugur soil series. Microbial properties (bacteria, fungi and actinomycetes population) decreased due to the application of CKD. The decrease in microbial population caused by the addition of CKD

is due to a decrease in organic C content. The application of the amendments increased the microbial population. Among the treatments, the addition of CKD (5 MT ha⁻¹) in conjunction with green manure increased the population of bacteria, fungi and actinomycetes. Application of CKD dust at a higher dose (10 MT ha⁻¹) decreased the microbial population (Table 5).

Table 5. Effect of CKD on soil microbial population (at 60 DAI) under lab study

Treatments	Bacteria X10 ⁵ cfu/ml		Fungi x10 ⁴ cfu/ml		Actinomycetes x10 ³ cfu/ml	
	Irugur soil series	Periyanaickenpalayam series	Irugur soil series	Periyanaickenpalayam series	Irugur soil series	Periyanaickenpalayam series
Control (absolute)	12	12	8	2	4	8
CKD@5 MT ha ⁻¹	5	10	4	1	3	6
CKD @10 MT ha ⁻¹	4	9	2	1	2	5
CKD@5 MT ha ⁻¹ +FYM@ 12.5 MT ha ⁻¹	15	9	10	3	5	11
CKD@5 MT ha ⁻¹ +Green manure@6.25 MT ha ⁻¹	17	12	12	4	7	13
CKD@5 MT ha ⁻¹ + Composted coir-pith @10 MT ha ⁻¹	15	10	10	2	6	11
CKD@5 MT ha ⁻¹ +Press mud @ 5 MT ha ⁻¹	16	8	11	3	5	11
CKD@10 MT ha ⁻¹ +FYM @12.5 MT ha ⁻¹	16	9	11	3	7	12
CKD@10 MT ha ⁻¹ + Green manure@6.25 MT ha ⁻¹	16	11	11	3	5	11
CKD@10 MT ha ⁻¹ + Composted coir-pith @10 MT ha ⁻¹	13	10	9	3	7	12
CKD@10 MT ha ⁻¹ +Press- mud @ 5 MT ha ⁻¹	15	9	10	3	6	12
SEd	0.9	0.7	0.4	0.3	0.8	0.6
CD	1.9	1.5	0.9	0.6	1.7	1.3

Table 8. Effect of cement kiln dust on grain yield, straw yield of rice var. ADT 43 under field experiment in red sandy soil

Treatments	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Straw yield (t ha ⁻¹)
T ₁	3.6	4.5
T ₂	4.2	4.4
T ₃	5.8	8.0
T ₄	5.7	7.8
T ₅	5.4	7.0
T ₆	3.4	4.5
T ₇	5.7	7.9
T ₈	5.8	7.8
T ₉	5.7	7.8
SEd	0.09	0.05
CD	0.20	0.11

Conclusion

The application of CKD alone at a higher quantity (10 MT ha⁻¹) negatively influenced bulk density, soil available N, and microbial properties. Application of CKD (5 MT ha⁻¹) in conjunction with amendments had a positive impact on soil properties. The application of CKD in red soil (Irugur soil series) increased soil pH whereas it decreased the soil pH in black cotton soil (Periyanaickenpalayam series). The CKD is rich in Ca, Mg, K, and Si and the application of

CKD improved the K content of the soil in the present study. Hence, further explorations are needed to substitute the CKD with K fertilizers for agricultural and horticultural crops, utilize the Si of CKD for improving the stable phytolith occluded C (phytOC) in soil, and reclamation of sodic soil, etc.

Conflict of interest: This experiment does not involve any animals; hence no conflict of interest.

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References

1. **Albahari, A.Y. Haitham , M.A., and Mohammed A., Hefni. (2022).** Cement Kiln Dust (CKD): Potential Beneficial Applications and Eco-Sustainable Solutions. *Sustainability*, 14(12),1-22
2. **Elbaz, A. A., A. M. Aboufotouh, A. M. Dohdoh, A.M.Wahba. (2019).** Review of beneficial uses of CKD, fly ash (FA), and their mixture. *J. Mater. Environ. Sci.*, 10 (11), 1062–1073
3. **Gulam, S., Khan, M.J., Usman, K. Rehman, H.U.(2010).** Impact of Press-mud as an organic amendment on physiochemical characteristics of calcareous soil. *Sarhad J. Agric.* 26(4);
4. **Kunal, Rafat Siddique, Anita Rajor, (2012).** Use of cement kiln dust in cement concrete and its leachate characteristics, *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 61, 59-68,
5. **Lamare, R.E, O.P. Singh. (2020).** Effect of Cement kiln dust on soil physic-chemical properties around cement plants. In Jaintia Hills Meghalaya. *Environ Eng Res*, 25(3): 409-417
6. **Mandal, S., Thangarajan, R., Bolan, N.S., Sarkar, B., Khan, N., Ok, Y.S., Naidu, R. (2016).** The biochar-induced concomitant decrease in ammonia volatilization and increase in nitrogen use efficiency by wheat. *Chemosphere*. 142, 120–127.
7. **Negim, O. Mustafa, A. Fouad. H.A. (2016).** Effect of pressmud as an organic fertilizer. On some soil properties, growth of tomato plants and infestation of *Tuta absoluta* under saline irrigation water. *J. Soil Sci. and Agric. Eng.* 7(8):557–563
8. **Prabakaran, C. (2021)** Maturity assessment of Market waste during composting *Multi logic in Science*.
9. **Prabakaran, C., (2006).** Impact of some organic N sources on soil physical properties and yield of tomato. *Madras Agricultural Journal* (1-6),46–52
10. **Prabakaran, C., (2007).** Influence of Organic N sources on Tomato. *J. of Eco. Biol.* 21 (1), 87-91
11. **Prabakaran, C., (2019).** Effect of CKD on soil health. (2019). In: *Natl. conference on Environmental pollution control technologies* Annamalai University 2019, PP.355–355
12. **Rodd, A. V., K. B. McRae, J. A. MacLeod, P. R. Warman, and M. G. Grimmett. (2009).** *Can. J Soil Sci.* 90(1):201-213
13. **Seo, M, Lee S-Y, Lee C, Cho S-S. (2019).** Recycling of Cement Kiln Dust as a Raw Material for Cement. *Environments*. 6(10): 113
14. **Sett, R. (2017).** Flyash: Characteristics, problems, and Possible Utilization, *Advances in Applied Science Research*, 8 (3), 32–50
15. **Sunilkumar, RS Meena, Dinesh Jinger, HS Jatav and Tejram Banjara. (2017).** Use of pressmud compost for improving crop productivity and soil health. *Int. Journal of chemical studies*, 5 (2): 384-389
16. **Udayasoorian, C., Prabakaran, C. Thukkaiyannan P. (2007).** Quality assessment of bananas under fertigation. *Journal of Ecobiol.*, 221 (3):269-273.